

Synthesis of 3-(4'-Methoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl Citronellyl Ether and Related Structures

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Manuscript received 28 January 1985, revised 7 October 1985, accepted 2 April 1986

Substituted aromatic allyl citronellyl ethers (1-4) have been prepared and structures supported by spectral data. The compounds were tested for their juvenile hormone activity.

LITERATURE records¹⁻⁴ the synthesis of various juvenile hormone like substances possessing multifunctionalities. Vig *et al.*⁵⁻⁷ and others⁸⁻¹⁰ synthesised citronellyl and geranyl ethers with substituted benzene and heterocyclic systems. In the present communication, various substituted aromatic allyl citronellyl ethers (1-4) have been synthesised and characterised.

Ethyl-2-methyl-3(4'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylate (5; $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = CH_3$) was obtained in 65% yield by modified Wittig reaction⁹ with ethyl α -diethyl phosphonopropionate on *p*-anisaldehyde, having (*E*)-stereochemistry as revealed by downfield signal in its pmr spectra¹¹. The unsaturated ester (5) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to obtain 2-methyl-3(4'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl alcohol (4; $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = CH_3$) in 60% yield. Ir spectra showed prominent peaks at 3 490 (OH) and 780 cm^{-1} (substituted double bond). The allylic alcohol (6) was converted into 2-methyl-3(4'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl bromide (7; $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = CH_3$) with phosphorus tribromide in 55% yield. This bromide decomposed on vacuum distillation. Therefore, on further attempt was made to purify it by distillation under reduced pressure. However, it was chromatographed over basic alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) as eluent. The purity of the chromatographed product was checked on tlc. Ir spectra showed absence of absorption in the hydroxyl region (3 400-3 600 cm^{-1}), thereby confirming the disappearance of hydroxyl group. The final compound 2-methyl-3-(4'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl citronellyl ether (1) was obtained in 45% yield by formation of sodium salt of citronellol with sodium hydride in THF followed by addition of the corresponding bromide (7). The structure of 1 was confirmed by spectral studies (ir, nmr) and elemental analysis (Table 1).

The compounds (2-4) were similarly prepared by adopting the same sequence of reactions. 2-Methyl-3-(3',4'-dimethoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl citronellyl ether (2) was prepared by starting with 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and ethyl α -diethyl phosphonopropionate, and 3-(3',4'-dimethoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl citronellyl

- 1, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = OH$
- 2, $R_1 = OCH_3$, $R_2 = OH$
- 3, $R_1 = OCH_3$, $R_2 = H$
- 4, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = H$

ether (3) was obtained from 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and ethyl α -diethylphosphonoacetate. 3-(4'-Methoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl citronellyl ether (4) was prepared when *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde was reached with ethyl α -diethylphosphonoacetate. Compounds 2-4 showed satisfactory spectral data (Table 1) and corresponded to that reported in literature¹² and elemental analysis.

Experimental

Ethyl-2-methyl-3-(4'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylate (5; $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = CH_3$): To a mixture of sodium hydride (2.5 g, 50% emulsion in mineral oil) placed in

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (1-4)

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Yield %	δ	$\nu_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	
		C	H				
1	$R_1 = \text{H}(z)$, $R_2 = \text{CH}_3(d)$	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$	79.6 (80.0)	9.8 (10.1)	45	0.8-0.9 (3H, a), 1.1-1.2 (4H, m, b), 1.3 (1H, m, c), 1.6-1.95 (11H, m, d), 3.5 (2H, t, e), 3.75 (2H, s, f), 4.05 (3H, s, g), 4.8 (2H, m, h), 6.8-7.35 (4H, m, i)	1 050 (ether linkage), 815, 710 (substituted aromatic system), 790 (substituted double bond)
2	$R_1 = \text{OCH}_3(g)$, $R_2 = \text{CH}_3(d)$	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$	75.9 (76.3)	9.3 (9.8)	52	0.8-0.95 (3H, a), 0.95-1.11 (4H, m, b), 1.3 (1H, m, c), 1.65-2.1 (11H, m, d), 3.5 (2H, t, e), 3.75 (2H, s, f), 3.98 (6H, s, g), 4.7 (2H, m, h), 6.8-7.5 (3H, m, i)	1 070 (ether linkage), 820, 715 (substituted aromatic system), 790 (substituted double bond)
3	$R_1 = \text{OCH}_3$, $R_2 = \text{H}$	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$	75.5 (75.9)	6.3 (6.9)	56		1 060 (ether linkage), 815, 710 (substituted aromatic system), 790 (substituted double bond)
4	$R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{H}$	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$	78.9 (79.4)	9.5 (9.9)	48		1 050 (ether linkage), 820, 715 (substituted aromatic system), 780 (substituted double bond)

diethylene glycol dimethyl ether (75 ml), ethyl α -diethyl phosphonopropionate (11.9 g) was added dropwise below 20° with stirring and the reaction mixture stirred continuously till evolution of hydrogen gas ceased. To the resulting yellow solution, was added *p*-anisaldehyde (6.8 g) slowly below 8°. After the addition, the reaction mixture was further stirred for 3 h at room temperature and then warmed on a water-bath for another 2 h. The contents were cooled and decomposed with large excess of water. The organic material was extracted with ether and the residue on fractional distillation under reduced pressure gave (5; $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{CH}_3$) (7.21 g, 65%), b.p. 130°/10-12 mm (Found: C, 70.5, H, 6.8. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 70.9; H, 7.2%).

2-Methyl-3-(4'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl alcohol (6; $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{CH}_3$): To a fine and ice-cooled suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.95 g) in ether (100 ml) was added dropwise with stirring, the unsaturated ester (5; $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{CH}_3$; 11g) in ether (150 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, and after cooling, the contents were decomposed with sodium potassium tartarate (10%, 25 ml). The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (3 × 100 ml), washed with water and dried. After evaporation of the solvent, the residue on distillation under reduced pressure afforded the unsaturated alcohol (6; $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{CH}_3$) (5.31 g, 60%), b.p. 150°/10-12 mm (Found: C, 73.8; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 74.2; H, 7.8%). Its spectrum showed no absorption in carbonyl region but exhibited prominent peaks at 3 490, 2 960, 1 605, 1 580, 1 490, 1 390, 1 370, 1 230, 1 050 and 780 cm^{-1} .

2-Methyl-3-(4'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)allyl bromide (7; $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{CH}_3$): A solution of the allylic alcohol

(6; $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{CH}_3$; 8.9 g) and phosphorus tribromide (6.8 g) in dry ether (100 ml) was refluxed till no more hydrogen bromide gas evolved. The contents were put in ice-cold water. The organic material was extracted with ether, and washed successively with water, sodium carbonate solution (5%) and water, and dried. Evaporation of the solvent gave the bromide 7 (6.6 g, 55%). The bromide (7) on distillation under vacuum decomposed. Therefore, no further attempt was made to purify it by vacuum distillation. However, it was chromatographed over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) as eluent in order to separate it from the alcohol. The compound showed no ir absorption in the region 3 400-3 600 cm^{-1} , thereby confirming the disappearance of hydroxyl group.

General procedure for preparation of title compounds (1-4): To a stirred solution of sodium hydride (10 mmol) in dry THF (50 ml) was added citronellol (10 mmol) in THF (10 ml) and stirring continued for 2 h. The corresponding bromide (10 mmol) dissolved in dry THF (10 ml) was then added and the contents stirred for 10 h at room temperature. The mixture was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with ice-cold water and the organic material was extracted with ether and washed with saturated solution of sodium chloride. Evaporation of the solvent resulted the desired ether. The compounds were purified by chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) as eluent.

Biological activity: The compounds were tested^{1,3} for their juvenile hormone activity on *Spodoptera litura* (Fab.) in the 5th and 6th instar

stages of the larvae. The early 5th instar and early 6th instar larvae showed no response when treated with 1000 ppm of the compounds. The compounds were also tested at the prepupa and newly emerged adults of the insect, but in these cases also the insects did not show significant activity.

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